

Control of leaf blast by treating seeds with CGA49104. Left, 6-week-old plants from untreated seed; right, 6-week-old plants from seed treated with CGA49104 at 8 g/kg seed.

were covered with polyurethane sheets for 3 consecutive nights to create an environment optimum for rapid blast development. The number of lesions per seedling was determined starting at 3 weeks after seeding.

In several preliminary experiments benomyl 50 WP at rates of 8 to 40 g/kg

seed gave 71 to 100% leaf blast control for 3 to 5 weeks. Effective as seed treatments in preliminary screening trials were CGA40104 50 WP (Ciba-Geigy Werke Schweizerhalle AG, Switzerland), PP389 (4,5-dihydro-4-methyltetrazole [1,5-a quinazolin-5-one], Imperial Chemical Industries, Ltd., Fernhurst,

England), and thiophanate-methyl.

Several experiments were conducted to compare the effectiveness of the four fungicides as seed treatments.

All four fungicides controlled leaf blast (see table). CGA49104 was the most effective and benomyl 50 WP, the least. Seed treatment with CGA49104 reduced blast by as much as 99% at both the 8 and 4 g/kg seed rate 6 weeks after seeding (see figure). The PP389 and thiophanate methyl formulations resulted in 97 and 72% control of blast, respectively. Phytotoxicity was noted with the higher rates of benomyl 50 WP, CCA49104, and PP389. Plants treated with benomyl 50 WP and PP389 at 40 g/kg seed showed temporary blighting of the leaf tips. The treatment with CGA49104 at 16 to 40 g/kg seed showed slightly delayed germination. At 32 to 40 g/kg seed, the fungicide slightly reduced percentage of germination.

The results suggest that treatment with several fungicides already available commercially or being developed can control leaf blast to acceptable levels early in the growing season. Furthermore, expanded fungicide screening may identify compounds that protect against leaf blast throughout most of the season, or that control blast completely throughout the season, by the relatively inexpensive seed-treatment technique. ■

Histochemical studies of the toxicity of carbofuran to brown planthopper

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Brown planthoppers (BPH) treated topically with carbofuran exhibited typical symptoms of carbamate insecticide poisoning: hyperactivity, convulsion, and paralysis.

On the basis of ED₅₀ (mean effective dose) and LD₅₀ (mean lethal dose) values obtained at different time intervals after treatment, carbofuran could reach the site of action within 30 minutes and kill the insect within 2 hours.

Histochemical demonstrations of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity and

inhibition by carbofuran were observed using thiocholine incubated with cryostat-frozen sections of BPH. AChE activity was detected only in the central nervous system (CNS). Its inhibition in the peripheral region of the CNS was closely related to symptoms of carbofuran poisoning. AChE activity in dead BPH treated with carbofuran and two other carbamate insecticides methomyl and MTMC — was recovered. On the other hand, its inhibition by diazinon was more obvious; after the death of the BPH no recovery of AChE activity was detected.

The similarity in patterns of inhibition of AChE activity in both brain and thoracic ganglia indicated that carbofuran was translocated throughout the body via the hemolymph.

The preferential inhibition of the

peripheral AChE activity of CNS was due, not to differential penetration of carbofuran to the site, but probably to the difference in sensitivity or intrinsic activity of AChE located in the peripheral and central regions.

In vitro experiments showed that AChE from the thorax of the BPH was more susceptible to carbofuran inhibition than that from the head. ■

Parasitic nematodes in continuously cropped uplands

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Plant growth and vigor progressively

declined at the Makassa farm, site of the upland experimental fields of the Rokupr Station, where rice had been continuously planted since 1974. The 1978 crop was markedly stunted, and affected plants had short, fibrous, and discolored roots. The long, plump, and light-colored roots typical of healthy plants were conspicuously absent.

The following parasitic species were found in soil samples examined:

Nematode	No./liter
<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp.	262
<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp.	174
<i>Rotylenchulus</i> sp.	178
<i>Criconemoides</i> sp.	115
<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.	67
<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp.	39
Total	835

The exact influence of the nematodes on the decline in plant growth and vigor has not yet been determined. In a 1978 test, yields of plots treated with the soil fumigant D-D were four times those of untreated control plots.

The soil pH at the site declined from about pH 5.2 in 1974 to pH 4.2 in 1978. Other organisms, including fungi and bacteria, were also isolated from the roots of affected plants.

F. E. Caveness, nematologist, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, assisted in identifying the nematodes. ■

Relationship between incidence of brown planthopper and rice stem rot pathogen

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The exploratory, feeding, and ovipositional punctures of the brown planthopper (BPH) seem to predispose rice plants to fungal and bacterial infections. Although information on this possibility is not definite, infection of BPH-infested plants by two mold fungi — *Cladosporium* sp. and *Dematium* sp. — has been reported. Stem rot disease caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* Tullis, a wound pathogen, might

Correlation between brown planthopper (BPH) and stem rot disease, Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, 1973 kuruvai.

Productive tillers (no.)	BPH adults and nymphs (no.)	Sclerotia (no.)	BPH location from plant base (cm)
8	17	7	5
7	27	10	10
9	40	10	12
8	40	58	10
7	47	50	12
8	50	50	8
9	51	50	15
11	55	100	12
14	55	170	15
9	62	70	18
11	65	70	10
6	80	75	8
9	87	75	10
12	90	70	15
15	100	140	10
8	105	150	12
5	107	140	10
8	110	120	8
9	127	155	15
7	160	170	12

occur in BPH-damaged portions of the plant. Therefore, a study was conducted in 1974 kuruvai to determine possible relationships between BPH population and incidence of stem rot pathogen.

Twenty hills of the variety Triveni with high BPH populations and stem rot incidence were selected at the Annamalai University Experimental Farm. Adult and nymph hoppers and black bodies (sclerotia) were counted and the total number was used as the criterion for indexing.

The correlation between the BPH

population and the fungal disease was positive ($r = 0.80^{**}$). Because the stem rot pathogen is basically a wound parasite, its occurrence might be facilitated by damage from insects, by lodging, or by other injuries. The increases in BPH population coincide with increases in sclerotia number (see table).

Thus, when BPH occurs, efforts to combat the stem rot pathogen might be initiated along with BPH control measures. ■

Effect of fungicides on disease control in dapog

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Fungicidal control of rice seedling diseases in a dapog nursery was evaluated in December 1978. Seeds were sown at 1 kg/m². Fungicides were applied as a) a 12-hour wet-seed treatment b) a foliar spray at 10 clays after sowing (DS), and c) a soil drench at 10 DS. At 25 DS, the seedlings were observed for infection by diseases caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Fusarium* spp.,

Effect of fungicides on seedling infection in rice, Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Mean seedling infection ^a (%)		
	12-h wet-seed treatment	Foliar spray 10-DS	Soil drenching 10 DS
• <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> spp., <i>Phythium</i> spp. ^b			
Hinosan	30.7	31.2	34.0
Dithane R-24	32.3	29.6	40.5
Bavistin	39.2	30.1	32.3
Fytolan	32.7	26.6	43.6
Agallol	16.6	27.8	34.1
Difolatan	32.8	27.4	32.7
Control	44.3	44.3	44.3
• <i>Pyricularia oryzae</i> ^c			
Hinosan	34.23	41.39	13.48
Dithane R-24	20.55	17.27	12.31

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